

A Study on Psychological issues: Challenges of Employees

***Souparnika&** vidya.n**

Assistant Professor, CMCSrinivas University, PandeshwarMangalore, Karnataka, India

OrcidID:0000-0003-4649-2496; shivasouparnika@gmail.com

**Associate Professor, College of Social Sciences and Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India. Orchid ID: 0000-0002-3390-567X; E-mail: vidyakrithi.n@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Tight deadlines, massive workloads, micromanagement and uncertainty – all realities that make your employees want to cringe. Why? Because they all lead to stress. And if excessive enough, they could even cause employees to become fearful about their jobs and their future with company. Those emotions can be a slow poison to any business, not only affecting employee health but also their levels of production. That's why, it's imperative that we should learn how to manage stress and fear at work. In order to do so, we need to understand workplace stressors and recognize fear within employees – from the hardest-working employees to most reserved. For instance, as a hard deadline creeps up, someone under duress may begin to panic. They scramble to finish and are succumbed to fear, asking themselves, "What if this isn't good enough? Will I be reprimanded? Should I just quit now?" or worse, "Will I be fired?"

In a state of fear, people compromise their ability to process thoughts and situations rationally. For some, their natural reaction is either fight or flight. Fight could be confronting their boss and demanding something. Or flight, keeping their head down and avoiding their boss all together.

My Paper Concentrates on Psychological issues and Challenges faced by employees at work and suggests some solutions based on the study.

Key words: *Employees, Psychological Issues, Work, Health.*

I. INTRODUCTION :

"No one can have everything and do everything at the same time". Psychologist - Oprah Winfrey
At present, work environment has become more stressful because of diverse role expectations, cut throat competition, globalization and technological innovations. Such changes have created several complications on both the domestic and professional fronts of the employees. The pressure of work has been intensifying and there is growing feeling among employees that the demands of work begin to dominate life and sense of work-life balance is felt. The challenge of integrating work and family life is a part of everyday reality for the majority of employees now-a-days.

There should be balance between an individual's work and his life outside work and this balance should be healthy. It is all about employees achieving a satisfactory equilibrium between work and non-work activities (i.e, parental responsibilities and wider caring duties, as well as other activities & interests). Changes in the social, political and economic fabric of societies have influenced and continue to influence both the nature of employment and its relationship to life outside work. The concept of Work-life balance is becoming more and more relevant in an ever-dynamic working environment.

In contrast, work-life conflict is a demand in a form of inner role conflict, in which role pressures from the work and other life domains, such as family, are mutually incompatible in some respect, whereby participation in one role is made more difficult by the virtue of participation in the other. Initially, the concept of work-life conflict was focused on impact of family demands on work. It now extends to the impact; work has on individual stress, relationship and family wellbeing.

Today, the new age workforce comprises mostly of knowledge workers, who are techno-savvy, aware of market realities, are materially focused and have a higher propensity to switch jobs. The increasing emphasis on knowledge-based competitiveness in the current turbulent environment also accelerated the

importance of human capital and Retention of Right Candidates is a challenging task to many employers. We live in stressful times, and each of us deals with stress every day. Scientists agree that moderate amount of stress can be benign, even beneficial, and most people are equipped to deal with it. However, increasing levels of stress can rapidly lead to low employee morale, poor productivity, and decreasing job satisfaction. Some of the specific symptoms that relate directly to productivity in the work environment are abuse of sick time, cheating, chronic absenteeism, distrust, organisational sabotage, tardiness, task avoidance, and violence in the workplace. Other serious repercussions are depression, alcohol and drug abuse, marital and financial problems, compulsive eating disorders, and employee burnout. Stress in the workplace had emerged as a major issue for businesses and it has reached alarming proportions. Work-related stress can affect individuals when they feel an inability to cope or control demands placed within their work environment and can eventually contribute to the development of maladaptive behaviours such as drinking and smoking and physical conditions such as depression, anxiety, nervousness, fatigue and heart disorders.

As conceptualized earlier, work and family life are separate domains having no bearing on each other however, it is now recognized that domestic identities and responsibilities sometimes spill over into the workplace and organizational identities and responsibilities often cross into home life. Whereas personal or family lives, interfere with work are associated for fewer hours as compared to the work that interferes with life matters. However, employee's attitudes towards their hours of work, and perceptions and complaints about work-life imbalances actually deals with working time and complaints about time pressure which are unrelated to hours, actually worked. A well-balanced integration of professional and private life is an essential goal for the new generation. Moreover, informal arrangements and managerial discretion are important in realizing work and care balance. Work-life balance and stress go hand in hand. What seems to matter in this regard is the importance workers place on balance in their lives and the effectiveness of workplace policies and practices in supporting them to achieve this goal.

II. OBJECTIVES:

1. To identify the determinants of Employee's Work- Life Balance.
2. To Understand Present Generation Reactions and Expectations towards stress in WLB.
3. To suggest the roles and responsibilities of key parties for maintaining WLB at workplace.
4. To recommend various ways to employers for overcoming work stress.

Determinants of Work-life Balance:

Following determinants have been identified which impact the issue of employee's work life balance.

- Organizational Factors
- Present annual income of employee
- Tenure in the present organization
- Department in which an employee is working
- Type of organization
- Nature of Job
- No. of years of previous experience
- Level of hierarchy in the organization
- Term of Contract
- Situational factors (like unreasonable & conflicting demands etc.)
- Unclear responsibilities and expectations
- Support from employer and management
- Support from colleagues
- Policies of organization
- Technology and its use
- Long Working Hours

- Excessive workload etc.

Individual Factors

- Age of an employee / Life Stage of Employee.
- Marital Status
- No. of Members of family
- Type of Family / Family Structure
- No. and Age of the kids
- No. of Dependents
- Educational Qualification
- Mobility from native place
- Attitude and values of employee
- Psychological factors
- Support from family members
- Energy Levels of employee
- Self-High Expectations

III. SUGGESTIONS TO OVERCOME STRESS AND TO HAVE A BALANCED WORK LIFE:

A number of recommendations, based on current thinking and empirical literature may assist readers to work towards making work-life balance both a strategic goal and a reality in their organizations.

1. Rather than classifying the workweek as five days or Six days long, allow employees to work four 10-hour shifts. This schedule enables employees to have three days off each week instead of the typical two-day weekend.
2. When possible, incorporate a work-from-home policy. Offering this benefit even a few days per year can make a difference.
Make day care available to staff on-site or incorporate a benefit which would provide day care at a discounted rate.
3. Offer a tax preparation service benefit.
4. Offer free gift-wrapping services during the holidays and for special occasions.
5. Consider high-performers and present family vacation packages in addition to, or in place of, monetary bonuses.
6. Offer concierge services to help employees balance the many errands in life.
7. Offer scheduling of flexitime, where employees can provide their input on their preferred work schedule (7 a.m. to 4 p.m., 8 a.m. to 5 p.m., 9 a.m. to 6 p.m.). If multiple employees request the same shift, offer a rotating schedule to satisfy everyone.
8. Offer seasonal hours, where employees can leave early on Fridays during certain seasons.
9. Make yearly anniversaries with the company an extra paid time off day to encourage employees to celebrate their tenure. This day off will also serve as a reminder that their employer cares.
10. Encourage employees to avoid checking their work e-mail and voice mail after the workday and on weekends, to separate work from their personal lives.
11. Allow employees to take a longer lunch, if they come in early or work later, to make up the missed time. This option will make it easier for staff to schedule appointments or run errands on their break.
12. Hold virtual meetings, so employees do not have to be on-site to attend.
13. Encourage employees to take frequent breaks to rehydrate and go to the restroom (at least once every two hours). This may seem unnecessary to address, but many busy people forget to take time out of the day for their personal wellbeing. While you may not be able to initiate all of these suggestions, even tackling a few will help employees see your organization's concern for true work-life balance in the workplace. Address these recommendations with your leadership team as soon as possible to tailor your approach and set your plan into action.

14. Let them know how you feel, too. Be transparent. Tell them if you're also scared or worried. Share some of your own stressors. This builds trust with employees faster than anything.

15. It's never too late to adjust your leadership style to better support your employees. Try new things with your team and see what works.

For example, consider if meetings are more effective in the early morning or late in the afternoon. Ask employees how they feel and adjust according to their needs and wants.

16. As a leader, it's important to be the support system your people need. Communicate with them often. Hear them out. Share your own tips for reducing stress and fear.

Here are some ideas to suggest:

- Encourage more breaks – Don't work non-stop for 8 hours
- Establish a "groove" – Learn what hours you work best, so you can be more effective and more productive
- Don't play the "what if" game – Don't worry about things that haven't happened or things you have no control over
- Count to 10 first – This allows your brain time to fully process the situation
- Be aware of your hot buttons – Know your triggers, so you can control your responses

IV. EUSTRESS VS. DISTRESS:

Stress is not always a bad thing. Stress is simply the body's response to changes that create taxing demands. There is a difference between eustress, which is a term for positive stress, and distress, which refers to negative stress.

Eustress, or positive stress, has the following characteristics:

- Motivates, focuses energy.
- Is short-term.
- Is perceived as within our coping abilities.
- Feels exciting.
- Improves performance.

Distress characteristics:

- Causes anxiety or concern.
- Can be short- or long-term.
- Is perceived as outside of our coping abilities.
- Feels unpleasant.
- Decreases performance.
- Can lead to mental and physical problems.

V. EXAMPLES OF EUSTRESS AND DISTRESS:

It is somewhat hard to categorize stressors into objective lists of those that cause eustress and those that cause distress, because different people will have different reactions to particular situations. However, by generalizing, we can compile a list of stressors that are typically experienced as negative or positive to most people, most of the time.

Examples of negative personal stressors include:

- The death of a spouse.
- Filing for divorce.
- Losing contact with loved ones.
- The death of a family member.
- Hospitalization (oneself or a family member).
- Injury or illness (oneself or a family member).
- Being abused or neglected.
- Separation from a spouse or committed relationship partner.
- Conflict in interpersonal relationships.
- Bankruptcy/Money Problems.
- Unemployment.
- Sleep problems.
- Children's problems at school.
- Legal problems.

Examples of positive personal stressors include:

- Receiving a promotion or raise at work.
- Starting a new job.
- Marriage.
- Buying a home.
- Having a child.
- Moving.
- Taking a vacation.
- Holiday seasons.
- Retiring.
- Taking educational classes or learning a new hobby.

Work and employment concerns such as those listed below are also frequent causes of distress:

- Excessive job demands.
- Job insecurity.
- Conflicts with teammates and supervisors.
- Inadequate authority necessary to carry out tasks.
- Lack of training necessary to do the job.
- Making presentations in front of colleagues or clients.
- Unproductive and time-consuming meetings.
- Commuting and travel schedules.

Stressors are not always limited to situations where some external situation is creating a problem. Internal events such as *feelings* and *thoughts* and *habitual behaviors* can also cause negative stress.

Common internally caused sources of distress include:

- Fears: (e.g., fears of flying, heights, public speaking, chatting with strangers at a party).
- Repetitive Thought Patterns.
- Worrying about future events (e.g., waiting for medical test results or job restructuring).
- Unrealistic, perfectionist expectations.

Habitual behaviour patterns that can lead to distress include:

- Overscheduling.
- Failing to be assertive.

- Procrastination and/or failing to plan ahead.

What are three simple things one can do to achieve work-life balance?

Just remember A-C-E, "ace": Awareness, Choice and Energy. This 3-step process is simple, does not cost any money and doesn't take any more time out of busy day. Its power lies in its simplicity.

A. Deepen your awareness through listening deeply and noticing two things: what throws you off balance, and what brings you calm and fulfilment. AWARENESS- Being mindful, present in your life.

B. Exercise the power of choice. Choose to release what drains you and embrace what truly nourishes you. When you begin to make life giving choices in your life, you will be able to make many more decisions easily. Realizing your life is the consequences of your choices becomes very empowering.

C. Reclaim the energy that is natural birth right. Your life will become a powerful dynamic concentric circle. The more aware you become, the more you become aware of your choices. The more you realize that your life is created by your choices, the more real energy and power you will experience in your life.

VI. CONCLUSION :

Job stress in any organisation has been increasing over the last few decades and has important implications for performances. Despite its importance, there has been a lack of proper stress management programs. As stress affects the outcome of productivity, monitoring and managing job stress is extremely important. It is primarily the responsibility of an individual to balance work and life and initiate steps to reduce stress and burnout. The organization can indeed facilitate the process. The individual has to explore his values, aspirations, and goals to understand what he expects from work and life and then develop the suitable ways of balancing work and life. Hence, he has to introspect on his job contents, ways of coping and relationship management. On the other hand, organization can initiate cutting edge work-life balance practices to help the employees“ manage their affairs more effectively. It can also train employees to understand the issues of worklife and stress management assistance programmes. Even with the availability of employee assistance programs in organisation such as stress management and flexible work arrangements, the complex nature of stress still seems to influence the health and work-life balance negatively. So it is the responsibility of the employer and employee to contribute to the better work-life balance for fruitful productivity.

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